

1 **PI3K subunit composition in metastasis to the lymph nodes in humans with breast cancer.**

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6 We measured total transcription in the primary tumor the lymph node (“regional” metastasis) in humans
7 with breast cancer to identify genes responsible for dissemination to the lymph nodes in invasive disease.
8 Components of the phosphatidylinositol-3 kinase (PI3K) signaling pathway were identified as activated
9 upon metastasis to the lymph nodes. These components included genes encoding pathway receptors
10 such as *PIK3R5* and *PIK3R4*. Other notable genes activated included *PIK3C3* and *PIK3C2B*. We
11 describe induction of a PIKFYVE complex effector *VAC14* in lymph node metastasis in human cancer.

12 Citations

13 1. Garmy-Susini B, Avraamides CJ, Desgrosellier JS, Schmid MC, Foubert P, Ellies LG, Lowy AM,
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